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D6.1 Operation strategy, limitations and
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Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to identify the key stakes and drivers for exploiting a flexible use of the MSR. To this end, a trade study has been led between all contributors of this task, identifying limitations and opportunities related to the operating conditions of different MSR concepts. Three kinds of MSR concepts have been considered for this study, each of them representative of certain design principles, relevant to flexibility issues.

Keywords

European Molten Salt Reactor Designs, MSR, flexibility, cogeneration.

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1 Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to identify the key stakes and drivers for exploiting a flexible use of the MSR. To this end, a trade study has been led between all contributors of this task, identifying limitations and opportunities related to the operating conditions of different MSR concepts. Three kinds of MSR concepts have been considered for this study, each of them representative of certain design principles, relevant to flexibility issues.

Section 2 describes the main requirements that different end users of a given reactor can impose, these end users being either a grid operator, or a specific industry with corresponding temperature or power needs.

Section 3 describes the trade study method, which was used in the frame of this task. A trade study must follow a definite set of steps in order to identify the most relevant criteria leading to a successful comparison between candidate solutions.

Section 4 describes the application of this method, in order to compare different MSR types in terms of expected performance regarding flexibility requirements.

2 Main context: MSR and flexibility requirements

Electrical power generation systems (nuclear based or not) connected to the grid are increasingly being required to have ramping and load following capabilities in order to adjust output so that grid utilities may ensure a balance between electricity supply and demand throughout the day. This is labelled as Flexible Power Operation (FPO), and ranges from frequency control operations to substantial load following.

With the rise and penetration of Variable Renewable Energy (VRE) sources, like wind and solar, which are often labeled as *non-dispatchable*, the need for flexibility in the nuclear fleet is more and more stringent, as the adjustment of supply and demand towards a constant balance is a requirement for frequency and voltage stability over a given network.

This translates into a set of requirements for power plants: those requirements may vary from country to country inside the EU but are ultimately expressed in terms of normal operation transients that a unit is supposed to be able to perform during the totality of its operational lifespan.

For defining the FPO Operational Performance, it is needed to establish the plant's ability to vary power output in response to grid demand using the following four parameters [6]:

- Rate: The rate at which a plant can change power levels over time.
- Depth: The extent (% of full power) of a power reduction a plant can make while still having the capability to return to the initial power level.
- Duration: The length of time that a plant will maintain a given power level.
- Frequency: The frequency of significant changes to a plant's power levels.

The European Utilities Requirements (EUR) Association aims at contributing to safe, competitive, and licensable nuclear new build projects in Europe through harmonized requirements and assessments of future Nuclear Power Plant designs, and strong interactions with vendors and regulatory bodies [7]. For instance, the EUR describe flexibility requirements for new LWRs and are summarized in the following table [8]:

EUR Requirements	Criteria
Continuous operation (mandatory)	50%-100% P_r with 3-5%/min. variation rate
Down to minimum (option)	20%
Primary control (mandatory)	$\pm 2\%$ P_r /min
Primary control (recommended)	$\pm 5\%$ P_r /min
Activating total primary range of control requested	within 30 s
Secondary control (option) seconds to minutes	$\pm 10\%$
Support grid restoration with sudden load steps of up to	10% of P_r .
Secondary control (optional)	$\pm 10\%$ of P_r , with a variation rate of 1% of P_r /min.
Load-following capability until () % of whole fuel cycle	90%
Full power to minimum load variations and back to full power operation	2 per day 5 per week Cumulatively 200 per year
Emergency load variation (agreement grid operator and unit operator)	20% P_r / min. (decreasing) 1-5% P_r / minute (increasing)

Table 1: EUR requirements for LWRs. P_r stands for rated power.

On the other hand, some recent nuclear projects (including startup projects) also position themselves not in terms of power production to a grid, but in terms of heat and/or power production towards industrial processes or district heating. The corresponding requirements become highly dependent on the corresponding industrial application. It should however be noted that most of these requirements translate into temperature ranges (necessary to maintain a given industrial process) instead of power ramps (necessary to maintain balance within a highly complex grid). Table 2 below describes the main temperature requirements from various industrial applications as well as the type of reactors able to provide such temperature loadouts.

Reactor type	Max. required steam / heat temperature	Relevant applications	Minimum temperature range needed
Water reactors	250°C	District heating	70-130°C
		Desalination	100-130°C
Fast breeders	450°C	Pulp & Paper	100-250°C
		Oil refining	500-550°C
High temperature reactors	550-650°C (secondary steam)	Chemicals	500-550°C
	<750°C (secondary gas)	Fertilizers	500-600°C
		Hydrogen (thermochemical production technology)	750-850°C
Very high temperature reactors	1000°C	Other applications	>1000°C

Table 2: Main temperature requirements from industrial applications

3 The Trade Study methodology

3.1 General presentation

Trade Studies are a System Engineering (SE) tool used by multidisciplinary teams in order to identify the most balanced technical solutions among a set of proposed viable solutions. Its objectives are the following:

- To be able to choose among alternative designs with uncertain or only partial information available.
- To make use of a multidisciplinary team, in order to benefit from a diversity of points of view on a given technical question.
- To identify key differentiating features between alternatives (among which the existence of a *killer* criterion, excluding a solution).
- If choice is not possible between alternatives (or too narrow), to identify priority studies to be launched in order to be able to eventually differentiate candidate solutions.

The name comes from the fact that early design studies will often result in a tradeoff between performance, cost and risk when trying to find a satisfactory solution. Trade studies are a valuable tool in many fields of engineering (from aerospace to software development) to find the configuration (or design option) that best meets sometimes conflicting performance requirements.

Though they may be performed at any step of a given system's lifecycle, trade studies are often conducted at early stages of design, when quantified information can be scarce. In this context, expert's points of view are extremely valuable, and a well-defined method can be necessary to channel them into a decision-making process.

Trade Studies provide a metric for comparing chosen criteria first, and ultimately a quantified way to compare candidate solutions relatively to one another. Though not always conclusive, this method also points towards fields of research of interest for future studies on the same subject.

3.2 Detailed process

Ways for conducting trade studies can vary (e.g. see [10]), but the core principle remains very similar. It consists in a cross-evaluation of candidate solutions to a design problem with a set of weighted selection criteria under the form of a matrix. In the frame of the ISAC project, Trade Studies have been conducted in order to select among preliminary design possibilities. The Trade Study performed in the frame of ENDURANCE follows the same process, illustrated by Figure 1:

Figure 1: Step-by-step process of a trade study

The corresponding steps are described in detail in subsections hereafter.

3.2.1 Step 1: choice of candidate solutions and identification of the *Musts*

The definition of the *Musts* criteria has the objective of identifying and thus rejecting any solution which does not comply with mandatory technical or safety requirements. This preliminary phase is used as a basis for the study: it bounds the space in which alternatives can be selected for examination. It also sets up the baseline and therefore confirms the choice of the candidate solutions, as adequate possibilities for the final choice at the end of the process.

The identification of the candidate solutions also constitutes a fundamental step to the process and should be carefully conducted. The alternatives can be composed of different versions or design of the same concept: they need to be similar enough in order for their comparison to be relevant, and for the chosen criteria to apply to every alternative. However, their choice must also reflect a form of diversity in order for the trade study to be of effective value in the design process.

3.2.2 Step 2: selection of criteria (*Wants*) and weight assessment

Once the candidate solutions have been selected, and their compliance with the *Musts* requirements verified, the set selection criteria (*Wants*) can be formulated by the team. In contrary to the requirements (*Musts*), the *Wants* can be partially met by alternatives, the degree at which they are met being the measure for future evaluation. Their choice is therefore also fundamental for the trade study. Though difficult to achieve, independence between criteria should be searched. The cumulative number of candidate solutions and selection criteria (*Wants*) should remain limited, as every criterion added mechanically increases the size of the future decision matrix. Since every criterion is ranked against its neighbors, the number of comparisons to perform rapidly increases and can significantly lengthen the whole process past a certain number.

Once the set of *Wants* has been decided and confirmed, the weight selection phase can be conducted. It consists in a ranking of criteria by pairs each of them being confronted with every other. The ranking process consists in attributing a grade (on a scale from 1 to 5 in our case) showing the relative importance of a criterion with regards to every other. For instance, in the

case of a comparison between criteria A and B, a score of A1 would mean that criterion A is slightly more important than criterion B, whereas a score of B5 would mean that criterion B is extremely more important than criterion A). It thus results in a set of weights attributed to each criterion: the weight reflects the overall importance of the criterion and its future impact on the final decision.

The ranking phase is a collective process, conducted during a dedicated meeting. The grade of every pairwise tournament is chosen after discussion, consensually. Grading can include experts' judgement, but also quantified elements when available. The result of this phase is a triangular matrix (due to obvious symmetry in the process), along with the weight corresponding to each criterion.

3.2.3 Step 3: Cross-comparison, final ranking and choice / discussion

The final process of the trade study consists in the cross-comparison between the candidate solutions from step 1 with the weighted criterion from step 2. The objective of this phase is to quantify the adequation of each candidate solution to each weighted criterion. The resulting score, once summed along the different criteria, will result in a final grade for each solution.

This final grading allows a ranking between the candidate solutions, but this ranking itself does not constitute the end goal of the trade study. The score obtained by each candidate solution relatively to the others is also a matter of comment, two solutions very close in terms of score meaning the process did not completely succeed in providing sufficient differentiation.

Furthermore, the values of the weights obtained at the end of step 2 is also a valuable result from any trade study, as it helps pinpoint which set of criteria carries the most impact for future studies on the subject.

4 Operational aspects of MSR flexibility and comparison of concepts

As exposed, the Trade Study method has been used within the task 6.1 of the ENDURANCE project. The goal of this task is to identify the key stakes and drivers for exploiting a flexible use of the MSRs, as well as the limitations and opportunities related to the operating conditions of the MRS concepts and layout.

4.1 *Composition of the team and formulation of the Trade Study's main question*

The team was composed of 5 members:

- 2 members from Framatome,
- 1 member from CEA,
- 3 members from CNRS.

Members reflected a variety of disciplines linked with MSR technology, but mostly centered around plant operation, neutronics and thermal-hydraulics.

As exposed in Chapter 3, one of the main issues of a trade study is to correctly formulate the main questions to be treated, as well as to identify the *Musts*. In the present case, when dealing with MSR and flexibility, one fact immediately arises: there is not a single type of MSRs. Across numerous projects (European or not), different concepts of MSRs were developed with radically different features, some of them impacting the behavior of the reactor when dealing with flexibility requirements. In the frame of the ENDURANCE project and at the time of the writing of this document, no official reactor design is defined.

Therefore, distinction between types of MSRs is key in order to properly corner every aspect and possible challenge with regards to flexibility requirements. Collective analysis by the team based on the feedback of previous and current MSR projects, lead to identify three types of MSRs, each of them linked with specific features, relevant to flexibility issues:

- Type I reactor: High thermal power, fuel salt in forced convection,
- Type II reactor: Low thermal power, fuel salt in forced convection,
- Type III reactor: Low thermal power, fuel salt in natural convection.

As an important remark, it should be noted that the above items can be labelled as “archetypes” of reactors. This means they are not supposed to represent the totality of the many design features of their respective parent reactor, but only the most relevant ones when dealing with flexibility.

- Type I is inspired from the MSFR reactor (Molten Salt Fast Reactor), a design studied in the frame of the SAMOSAFER European project through which it has been extensively studied. From an operability and flexibility point of view, this design is characterized by its high thermal power (3000 MW_{th}), but also from the lack of control rods. Indeed, as stated in **Error! Reference source not found.**, it has been established since the Oak Ridge studies that reactivity control through rods during power variations was not necessary, and that load following could be achieved thanks to intermediary salt circuit mass flow variations. This would grant a simplified architecture of reactivity control means.

- Type II reactor is inspired from “ARAMIS” (Advanced Reactor for Actinide Management In Salt) reactor, the design of the ISAC project (Innovative System for Actinide Conversion), as described in reference [2]. Also, with power on the lower range (300 MW_{th}), its design incorporates reactivity control through dedicated devices, in contrary to MSFR design. Indeed, a set of rotating drums are located outside of the active core and contain neutron absorber on one of their sides. They can be turned for their absorbing side to face the active core, thus reducing reactivity. For illustration, a similar process is described in [9].
- Type III reactor is inspired from “Stellarium” reactor, the product of the startup Stellaria. This kind of reactor is characterized by a thermal power on the lower range (500 MW_{th}) and a natural convection operation. This fully passive operation does not require any mechanical pieces and is able to adjust to the power demand through neutron feedback mechanisms.

With this repartition in mind, the main question governing the trade study is the following:

Among the 3 defined archetypes of MSR (Type I, Type II, & Type III), which of them is the best suited for a usage with flexibility requirements (electricity production to a grid or cogeneration)?

The goal of the Trade Study is to provide elements of an answer to this question by distinguishing between the archetypes. The Trade Study process will help identify to which extent these archetypes are suited to flexibility constraints. It should also be noted that this Trade Study analysis does not assume any specific type of co-generation application. Indeed, a specific Trade Study dedicated to co-generation solution and flexibility will be lead in the frame of Task 6.2. The current task focuses solely on how a given MSR reactor should behave in order to respond at best to flexibility requirements in the general form of power ramps.

4.2 Identification of the Musts

As previously stated, the formulation of *Musts* is the preliminary phase consisting in defining non-negotiable requirements for the selection (or rejection) of candidate solutions. In our case, one possible move would be for our selection of *Musts* to stick to the usual requirements of a nuclear reactor, and of a MSR in particular. However, these would not reflect the specificity of the current study, centered around flexibility. Therefore, *Musts* were collectively chosen around the following themes:

- Safety: Safety requirements were selected and formulated around their link with flexibility and normal operation of the reactor. The corresponding *Must* requirements therefore state that safety margins should not be penalized by the flexible use of the reactor.
- Performance: Whichever option chosen at the end of the process, one key requirement is that global plant efficiency should remain competitive and not be negatively impacted by the flexibility requirements.
- Operation: Operation guidelines should not exceed in complexity those of PWRs.

Based on these core principles, a set of *Must* requirements was established, summed up in the following table.

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Category	Must Requirement
Performance & cost	The nominal state of the whole system (fuel salt, intermediary salt and energy conversion system) must meet satisfactory reactor efficiency values.
Performance & cost	Cost of flexibility and operating strategy must remain acceptable.
Safety	For all normal operation states: the safety margins related to the different thresholds (thermomechanical limits, freezing temperature of salt) must be large enough to provide leeway to operate the reactor.
Safety	The operating strategy must guarantee a safe operation of the reactor and allow limitation or correction of drifts without soliciting protection systems.
Safety	Stable behavior of the reactor in normal operation: limitation of parameter drifts.
Operation	General Operating The general operating requirements must not be more complex than those of an equivalent PWR
Operation	Technical Operating The specifications must not be more complex than those of an equivalent PWR

Table 3: Must requirements

4.3 Identification, comparison and ranking of the Wants

Following the workflow previously defined, the next step of the Trade Study was dedicated to the formulation and comparison of the *Wants* criteria pairwise in order to generate a matrix. These criteria were established collectively by the team during dedicated sessions. As for the *Musts*, the identified criteria can be gathered under categories, labelled as follows:

- Performance / efficiency
- Flexibility
- Operation
- Life expectancy
- Neutronic stability
- Costs

As previously described, the *Wants* criteria were collectively chosen and then compared during dedicated meetings. It is important to underline here that the outcome of a Trade Study at every step is unique since it reflects the composition of the team as well as the different discussions occurring during its successive phases.

It should also be noted that none of the following criteria are accompanied with quantified values. Indeed, the role of these criteria is to serve as a basis of relative comparison between candidate solutions, in order to determine which of them leans the closest to one or many *Wants*.

A total of 8 criteria were collectively described and labelled. They are summed up in the following table.

	Category	Description
A	Performance	Operating parameters of the reactor (fuel circuit, secondary circuit, and energy conversion system) should maximize reactor performance and efficiency in case of flexible use.
B	Operation	Reactor regulation systems should be fast and responsive.
C	Life Expectancy	Reactor parameters should be chosen towards minimization of thermomechanical constraints due to operating strategy.
D	Flexibility	The reactor should have a wide range of normal operation power.
E	Flexibility	From one power level to another, the reactor should be able to perform a wide range of power ramps in flexible normal operation.
F	Operation	The reactor should be able to respond freely (<i>ie</i> with very limited or even without any operator action) to power ramp solicitations for a limited range of power around its nominal value.
G	Stability	When responding to demands in a flexibility context (<i>ie</i> power ramps, transition from one reactor state to another), the reactor should enforce a neutronically stable behavior, with limited variations around the requested value.
H	Cost	The cost of flexible use of the reactor should be limited compared to constant nominal functioning.

Table 4: *Wants* criteria

The following elements were pointed out while elaborating this set of criteria:

- Many of these criteria (B, D, E) directly address flexibility issues. Indeed, flexibility requirements translate into power levels for the reactor to adjust to, as well as power ramps in between stable states. While frequency regulation transients (primary and secondary controls) can be dealt with by using turbine bypass (and therefore have no impact on the fuel circuit), load-following transients (whether dictated from grid requirements, or co-generation needs), will often result in power variations on the core side, for electricity-only flexibility.
- Neutron feedback mechanisms closely linking power and temperature variations within a MSR can result in unwanted unstable behavior during power ramps. The ability of the

reactor to be operated “freely” (i.e. making use of the natural behavior of the reactor to regulate itself and adjust its thermal power to output demand at ECS level), is one of the identified advantages of MSR (and identified by criterion F); Type III reactors previously defined integrate this ability in their design. For example, when the power requested at turbine level varies, this variation cascades into the secondary salt temperature, and subsequently the fuel salt temperature (primary circuit). Through the mechanism of neutronic counterreactions, the system eventually reaches a new stable state corresponding to the output power. Benefitting from this natural behavior somehow comes at a cost of temperature transients, whose amplitude and duration might not be compatible with flexibility requirements.

The following step of the Trade Study method consists in ranking these Wants by comparing them two by two. To this end, a triangular matrix is filled, as shown in Figure 2 below:

	Category	Description	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
A	Performance	Operating parameters of the reactor (fuel circuit, secondary circuit, and energy conversion system) should maximize reactor performance and efficiency in case of flexible use.	A1							
B	Flexibility	Reactor regulation systems should be fast and reactive.		B1						
C	Life expectancy	Reactor parameters should be chosen towards minimization of thermomechanical constraints due to operating strategy			C1					
D	Operation	The reactor should have a wide range of normal operation power.				D1				
E	Flexibility	From one power level to another, the reactor should be able to perform a wide range of power ramps in flexible normal operation.					E1			
F	Operation	The reactor should be able to respond freely (ie with very limited or even without any operator action) to power ramp						F1		
G	Stability	When responding to demands in a flexibility context (ie power ramps, transition from one reactor state to another), the reactor should enforce a neutronic stable behavior, with limited variations around the requested value.							G1	
H	Cost	The cost of flexible use of the reactor should be limited compared to constant nominal functioning.								H1

Figure 2: Wants ranking: empty matrix

As explained in section 3.2.2, each cell must be filled with a grade attributed by the team in a collective manner, on a scale of 1 to 5. This grade reflects how important a criterion is relative to another. For instance, when comparing criterion A with criterion B, the grade A5 would mean that criterion A is much more important than criterion B. Reciprocally, the grade B1 would mean that criterion B is very slightly more important than criterion A.

This step is capital in the process, as the final weight attributed to each criterion greatly impacts the result of the Trade Study. Directly comparing criteria with sometimes very different formulations and applications can prove to be a delicate task, hence the need for a collective consensus on each ranking.

The filled matrix with all the rankings is displayed on Figure 3 below:

	Category	Description	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
A	Performance	Operating parameters of the reactor (fuel circuit, secondary circuit, and energy conversion system) should maximize reactor performance and efficiency in case of flexible use.	A1	B3	C2	D1	E4	A2	G3	H2
B	Flexibility	Reactor regulation systems should be fast and reactive.		B1	B2	B1	E1	B3	G3	B1
C	Life expectancy	Reactor parameters should be chosen towards minimization of thermomechanical constraints due to operating strategy			C1	C3	C3	C4	G1	H3
D	Operation	The reactor should have a wide range of normal operation power.				D1	E2	D1/F1	G3	H3
E	Flexibility	From one power level to another, the reactor should be able to perform a wide range of power ramps in flexible normal operation.					E1	E5	G1	H1
F	Operation	The reactor should be able to respond freely (ie with very limited or even without any operator action) to power ramp						F1	G4	H3
G	Stability	When responding to demands in a flexibility context (ie power ramps, transition from one reactor state to another), the reactor should enforce a neutronically stable behavior, with limited variations around the requested value.							G1	G1
H	Cost	The cost of flexible use of the reactor should be limited compared to constant nominal functioning.								H1

Figure 3: Wants ranking: filled matrix

In order to better visualize the main tendencies of this ranking, Figure 4 shows the total score raised by each criterion, corresponding to the sum of the weights it was given in the matrix.

Figure 4: Total weights achieved by each criterion

The following points can be underlined:

- Criterion G, corresponding to the need for a stable behavior of the reactor across the different power variations it will be required to perform, ranks the highest. Indeed, stable behavior was deemed a priority by the team: when a power value is requested from the

grid or another end user, this value should be achieved by the reactor without any unwanted oscillations.

- On the other hand, criterion F ranks the lowest: free and natural response of the reactor (i.e. using the capacity of the reactor to regulate itself and adjust to the requirement) was not identified as a priority by the team. Fully controlled and timely response of the reactor to external demand was judged more important.
- The ranked criterion can be roughly separated in two categories of lower and higher ranks:
 - Criteria A, D and F with lower weight values.
 - Criteria B, C, E, G and H with higher weight values.

A lower weight value does not necessarily mean that the corresponding criterion is overall irrelevant; indeed, reactor efficiency and operability (endorsed by criteria A, D and F) are key parameters in a global design process. But in the frame of this Trade Study, criteria related to flexibility were judged of higher importance.

4.4 Final ranking

The last step of the Trade Study analysis is the cross-comparison of the candidate solutions with the set of weighed criteria. Each solution is given a grade (from 1 to 5) when confronted to each of the 8 criteria previously described.

The final ranking matrix to be filled by each participant (or group of participants) is described in Figure 5 below:

		Criteria									
		Score	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	
Alternatives	Percentage score	4.11	15.07	17.81	2.74	17.81	1.37	23.29	17.81	Total score	
Reactor Type I	Grade by criterion										
	Weighted score										
Reactor Type II	Grade by criterion										
	Weighted score										
Reactor Type III	Grade by criterion										
	Weighted score										

Figure 5: Final results: empty matrix

The grade attributed by the participant to the candidate solution regarding a given criterion will be multiplied by the weight of the corresponding criterion. The final grade of the solution will be the sum of these components over the criteria, allowing for comparison between the solutions.

Contrary to the weighing process of the criteria, this phase was performed by each entity (Framatome, CEA, CNRS) separately, and without communication with the rest of the team before comparison of the results. The corresponding result matrixes were then compared between entities. They are displayed hereafter.

The grades allocated by each entity were chosen based on the expected performance of the solution with regards to the different criteria, as well as the current knowledge of these possible performances. It should be noted that the maximal grade value of 5 was rarely granted, all team members judging that the technical maturity for MSRs concerning flexibility issues in general could still be improved.

All grades allocated by participants are summarized in an appendix available to the project partners. Concerning the Type-II reactor, the gradings take into account the current knowledge of such reactor types, mostly through the ISAC project. The overall grading of the “Type-II”

solution varies between 3,19 and 3,77. Main differences in grading come from the perception of criterion C (life expectancy) by the Framatome team, granting a lower grade than other teams. Indeed, Framatome granted low grades for all solutions for criterion C, noting that life expectancy was a common issue for all types of MSRs, due to radiation damage of structures dealt by the fuel circuit and potential chemical interactions (such as corrosion) between the salt and the primary and secondary circuits.

Concerning the Type III reactor, all teams invoked the lack of information about its ability to perform flexibility-related transients in the most efficient way, compatible with grid or industrial requirements (CNRS even chose to leave a blank on a criterion, pushing it out of the grading process). However, this reactor concept scored higher for criteria related to its ability to be operated with minimal human intervention (F), as well as its expected limited cost (H).

Concerning the other solutions, CEA and Framatome have placed the Type-II reactor slightly ahead of the Type I. The two solutions are close in terms of scores, the main difference in grading coming from criteria A and B. Indeed, these criteria are linked with reactor efficiency and how fast reactor regulation systems can respond to flexibility requirements. Underlying reasons for this choice stem from the differences between the two concepts regarding reactor power regulation, Type I reference reactor not using control rods, in contrary to Type II reference one which use dedicated devices such as rotating drums. This ranking was however not chosen by CNRS, which valued the better knowledge of MSFR capabilities concerning neutronic stability (quantitatively assessed in the frame of the SAMOSAFER project).

The completion of the Trade Study did not result in complete agreement on the overall ranking of the identified candidate solutions. However, it allowed to pinpoint the opportunities related to the implementation of flexibility in MSRs. Indeed, the ranking of the criteria and their impact on solution ranking help identify the most impactful fields for future studies: the stability of the power outlet of the reactor should be assessed, thanks to dedicated studies coupling thermal-hydraulics and neutronics. Limitation of these instabilities is mandatory in order to reduce unwanted thermal loadings on steel structures, ultimately limiting the life expectancy of the reactor itself.

5 Conclusion

A Trade Study was conducted in order to identify the opportunities and limitations related to flexible use of MSRs, in a global context of diversification of energy sources in grids, as well as diversification of application of nuclear reactors, including industrial uses.

The Trade Study method was applied, leading to identify three candidate solutions labelled as MSR types. The goal of the study was to identify which of these reactor types was better suited for responding to requirements in the context of a flexible use. Along the process, a set of eight criteria was selected by the team, dealing with reactor performance, stability, cost, operability. Solutions were then ranked across this set of sorted criteria. Although full consensus could not be achieved on the final ranking (with Type I or Type II reactor ranking first for different team members), the study helped pointing out possible priority fields for future studies, among which power stability within the fuel circuit when dealing with power variations.

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